

SZ-EB-I-01 Connecting a state-owned Moodle platform (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15437092
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Title	Connecting a state-owned Moodle platform
Educational area	#adult-education
Persona	P: Simon - Adult education https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261088
Short description	In order to improve the visibility and organization of teaching and learning opportunities in the field of teacher training, Simon wants to make selected Berlin training opportunities more visible and accessible via BIRD.
Result	BliQ's Moodle platform is connected to the BIRD middleware (data room + identity management). Simon can make the state platform's offerings more discoverable.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Inform about the training offers of other state institutes"• Part 2: "Feeding Berlin's training offers into the BIRD data room"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Simon is registered at BIRD• Simon is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder
Services / tools	#moodle

Problem scenario

Introduction

Simon Willand works as a teacher training consultant with a focus on digital schools at the Berlin State Institute for Qualification and Quality Development in Schools (BliQ). In his role, he coordinates teacher training programs and regularly works with the Moodle-based platform for digital continuing education and training in the state of Berlin (Lernraum Berlin). Simon's main task is to select suitable training programs and review their content for quality, didactic structure, and organizational structure. The training programs are then uploaded to Lernraum Berlin and made available there to teachers in the state of Berlin.

Problem definition

Simon has been working as a consultant at the state institute for many years. During his work, he repeatedly notices how difficult it can be, not only for himself, but also for colleagues and ultimately for teachers, to review and sort through the large range of professional development courses. In his daily work, Simon often struggles with the poor searchability of the materials available in the Berlin Learning Space and on other platforms. He has therefore longed for users of teaching and learning platforms to receive more quickly, tailored suggestions when searching for professional development opportunities and other relevant materials.

Simon not only wants to make BliQ's professional development courses more visible and searchable, but also compare them with those offered by other federal states to gain inspiration or simply gain a consistent overview. Greater transparency and networking with other state institutes in Germany are important to him in order to eventually create an even better professional development landscape for teachers.

Background and context

Education in Germany is a matter for the federal states. This also applies to teacher training and continuing education, meaning that each federal state has its own regulations regarding the provision and delivery of training courses. Especially in the digital context, federalism can lead to a sometimes severe fragmentation of standards. Each federal state has state institutes for education, which play a central role in the organization and implementation of teacher training. Simon works at BliQ, where courses are developed, monitored, and uploaded to state-specific learning management systems (LMS), such as Lernraum Berlin, for teachers from Berlin. The state LMS are generally based on Moodle.

State institutes operate largely independently of one another and have little or no access to the materials, course offerings, and LMS of the other federal states.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Simon has many years of experience working as a digitally teacher and speaker and understands the potential of well-structured teacher training and professional development, especially when it comes to digitizing school lessons. The federal fragmentation of the educational landscape, accompanied by a multitude of non-cooperating LMS and a lack of transparency, often frustrates him in his daily work. Due to the fragmentation of professional development programs fostered by federalism, parallel structures and inconsistent standards in teacher training sometimes arise. Multipliers and employees in educational institutions can be negatively impacted by the limited opportunities for cooperation and the lack of transparency.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Simon has already had many discussions with his colleagues at BliQ about how to improve the visibility of continuing education offerings in Berlin and create more transparency at the same time. However, he quickly realized that not only his colleagues, but BliQ itself, is subject to various institutional limitations. As a state institute, it must adhere to political guidelines and has little autonomy when it comes to collaborating with other federal states. Technical resources are also limited.

Another hurdle is that BliQ was only founded a few months ago. The state institute is still in its development phase, which leads to many structural and organizational hurdles. Therefore, Simon can only take small steps at the moment. However, he is in contact with a former colleague who works at the Brandenburg State Institute for Schools and Teacher Training (LIBRA). He discussed with him the possibility of BIRD using an interface to import various information on state-specific continuing education programs into a nationwide, shared data room.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Inform about the training offers of other state institutes"

Step 1: Simon has been using BIRD privately for some time and knows that he can use the LearningPathFinder to search for continuing education and training opportunities nationwide and then be redirected to the respective providers' websites. To make BliQ's offerings easier to find, he checks how BIRD can help him and navigates to the learningPathFinder.

Step 2: In the LearningPathFinder, Simon enters "training opportunities for teachers" in the free text search.

Step 3: The LearningPathFinder shows him the results of his search and Simon sees that training courses from other state institutes are displayed. He wonders how these get into the learningPathFinder and navigates to the FAQs to find out more.

Step 4: In the FAQs, Simon reads that BIRD has a shared data room in which, among other things, teaching/learning and training offers are entered.

Step 5: Simon returns to the LearningPathFinder search results. He would like to find out how the other state institutes whose training courses are displayed have solved the data protection problem.

Step 6: He clicks on an offer from the Brandenburg State Institute (LIBRA) to learn more about the training courses his colleague had told him about. He notices that he is only shown the name of the state institute, the title of the training course, the target audience, and the period in which the training takes place. This increases the visibility of the state institutes' offerings while simultaneously protecting data privacy.

Part 2: "Feeding Berlin's training offers into the BIRD data room"

Step 1: Simon remembers the conversation with his former colleague and therefore knows that metadata on training courses can be transferred to the data room via an interface.

Step 2: Simon contacts the IT department to discuss how they can transfer BliQ's offerings to the data room as efficiently and time-efficiently as possible. He also contacts his supervisor to find out whether his actions comply with data protection law.

Step 3: After receiving approval from his supervisor, Simon wants to start the transfer process. He finds the link "For providers: Participate in the data room now" on the LearningPathFinder homepage and is redirected to a contact form in the imprint where he can express his request.

Step 4: The data room team provides Simon and the IT team with access to the interface (API key) and the editorial environment (expert tool), and informs them of the metadata standards used. They can now publish excerpts from their database directly in the data room. Before the metadata is published, it goes through an automatic quality check.

Step 5: The BliQ materials are automatically contextualized based on the metadata. Simon can later use this contextual information using the editorial environment (the expert tool). This also makes it possible to represent affiliations and relationships between offerings/artifacts and to larger ordering schemes.

Step 6: Simon double-checks his entries. He is very satisfied with the automatic assignment and finally releases the training courses for the BIRD data room. Then he ensures that the LearningPathFinder only provides access to information on BliQ's training offerings that has been previously approved by his supervisor.